

An H I story of galaxies in A2626 and beyond

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In this diverse universe, galaxies are also observed in various shapes, sizes and colours. The cosmic environment of galaxies affects their properties, both during their formation and subsequent evolution involving interactions with their surroundings. In dense cosmic environments such as galaxy clusters, several physical mechanisms remove the atomic hydrogen gas (H I) discs of galaxies, resulting in quenching of the star formation activity in those galaxies. One of the most effective gas removal mechanisms acting on galaxies in clusters is ‘ram pressure stripping’[1] (RPS). This occurs when galaxies fall into the core of a cluster and encounter a head wind pushing the cold gas out of the galaxy, leaving the stars unaffected. Extreme examples of RPS are the ‘jellyfish’[2] galaxies that display ‘tentacles’ of gas that stretch far beyond their stellar discs and in which after new stars are born.

To investigate the morphological transformation and the quenching of star-formation of galaxies, we need to understand the physical processes of gas depletion and removal from galaxies. While the H I gas provides the raw fuel for star formation, the morphologies and kinematics of the extended, collisional and fragile H I gas discs of galaxies serve as sensitive diagnostic tracers of these environment driven gas depletion and removal processes[3, 4]. We have studied H I properties and morphologies of galaxies in and around A2626 cluster to investigate the environmental impact on the gas evolution and star formation activities of these galaxies.

Galaxies in and around A2626 cluster

Abell 2626 (A2626) is a moderately massive galaxy cluster ($M_{\text{halo}} \approx 5 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$) at a redshift of $z=0.0545$, which, due to its location within the cosmic web, as well as its own identified substructures[5], is an ideal laboratory to study galaxy transformation processes. A2626 is part of the WINGS imaging and spectroscopic survey[6, 7] and harbours a number of so-called ‘jellyfish’ galaxies[8], indicating an ‘active’ cluster environment. A2626 is embedded in a wall of the cosmic web and is close to cluster A2637 as well as a diffuse, filament-like structure behind the wall. An extensive MMT/Hectospec redshift survey[5] over a $2^{\circ} \times 2^{\circ}$ area has revealed that three main environments exist in and around A2626: 1) the cluster A2626 with a virialized population of galaxies, 2) various substructures inside the cluster, indicating recently accreted galaxy groups, and 3) a diffuse filament just behind the cluster with a collection of loose groups dubbed ‘the Swarm’. Volume-limited H I imaging data from a single MeerKAT pointing centred on A2626[9] revealed 219 H I detected galaxies with optical counterparts covering different cosmic environments. We have presented the H I properties of the detected galaxies with tables and an atlas page for each galaxy, including an H I column-density map, a velocity field, a position-velocity diagram, and a global H I profile.

Figure 1: H I deficiency vs. projected distance normalised by R_{200} for the non-substructure or isolated (green circles) and substructure (magenta circles) galaxies in A2626. Horizontal dashed lines present the range of H I deficiencies of the field galaxies. There is a clear correlation between H I deficiency and projected distance - H I deficient galaxies reside close to the cluster core.

H I morphologies of galaxies in A2626 and beyond

We have explored the relationship between H I deficiency, H I morphology, and star formation deficiency for the galaxies in and around the A2626 galaxy cluster. There are three main environments: non-substructure galaxies in A2626 (cluster environment), substructure galaxies in A2626 (groups influenced by the cluster environment) and the Swarm galaxies (group environment). The galaxies detected in H I with sufficient signal-to-noise and angular resolution are considered for our analysis. To quantify asymmetries of the outer H I disc of a galaxy, we used 1) three visual classes based on the outermost reliable H I contour: settled, disturbed, unsettled H I discs, 2) the offset between the H I centre and the optical centre of a galaxy, and 3) the modified asymmetry parameter A_{mod} [10]. The H I deficiency of a galaxy is correlated with the projected distance from the centre of A2626 cluster. This trend probably indicates an increase of gas removal efficiencies in the cluster core, similar to what previous observations have found[11, 12]. Moreover, substructure galaxies tend to be more asymmetric than the non-substructure galaxies in A2626, plausibly because of more efficient tidal interactions within substructures than outside substructures. Furthermore, asymmetric, offset, and smaller H I discs are not necessarily the result of the cluster environment, as they are also observed in substructures in A2626 and in the Swarm. This hints that ‘pre-processing’ of the H I discs of galaxies in groups or substructures plays an important role, together with the ‘processing’ in the cluster environ-

ment. Finally, the galaxies in all three environments have slightly lower star-formation rates (SFRs) than the typical SFR for normal galaxies as manifested by their offset from the star formation main sequence, implying effective gas removal mechanisms when the galaxies are both in group and cluster environment.

Figure 2: SFR vs H I mass for JFGs and JFCGs compared to the reference sample galaxies with the similar stellar mass range. Grey hexagons are galaxies from the xGASS sample (Catinella et al. 2010). Star and pentagon markers are JFGs and JFCGs respectively. JFGs are very H I deficient but their star formation is not quenched yet.

Jellyfish candidate galaxies in A2626

Within the MeerKAT surveyed volume in A2626, there are six plausible RPS or jellyfish candidate galaxies (JFCGs) from B-band optical images[13]. Two of the six galaxies JW100 and JW103 are confirmed as RPS galaxies from the H I observations. Both of these galaxies have low H I content, reside close to the cluster core, and move at very high velocities ($\sim 3\sigma_{cl}$). The other JFCGs, identified as non-jellyfish galaxies, are H I rich, their H I morphologies reveal warps, asymmetries, and possible tidal interactions. When we compared the H I content vs the SFR in both the RPS galaxies in A2626 and three other confirmed jellyfish galaxies from the GASP sample[14] with the reference sample galaxies, all five jellyfish galaxies stand out in the relation because of the lower H I masses for their SFRs. This signifies that in spite of having lost most of its gas reservoir, JFGs continue to form stars significantly.

Striking jellyfish galaxy JW100

JW100 is one of the most well-studied JFGs. We detect atomic (H I), molecular (CO), and ionised ($H\alpha$) gas tails of

similar extent (~ 50 kpc) in JW100. Comparing the multi-phase velocity channels, we do not detect any H I or CO emission in the northern part of the tail where $H\alpha$ and X-ray emission is present[15], possibly due to a prolonged interaction between the stripped gas and the inter-cluster medium. We also observe an anti-correlation between atomic and molecular gas, which signifies an efficient conversion of H I to H_2 in the southern part of the tail. We estimate that 80% of the H I gas has been removed and/or converted into H_2 by RPS. Of the remaining 20% of H I gas, we find 70% in the tail and 30% still in the disc. Thus JW100 is already at a very advanced stage of gas removal.

Figure 3: Multi-phase gas in the RPS tail of JW100. $H\alpha$ (white, 1" resolution) and H I (red, 20" resolution) contours are overlaid on the DECaLS color image.

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